

Communicating Awareness: Designing a Framework for Cognitive Human-Agent Interaction for Autonomous Vehicles

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ABSTRACT

Human cognition deals with uncertain real-world environments with appropriate situational awareness (SA), risk awareness, coordination, and decision making. On the other hand, current robotic agents, such as self-driving cars and drones, need to make decisions based on information beyond what can currently be incorporated in the human-based models of SA. These agents are meant to fulfill increasingly complex autonomous operations via multi-layer computational reasoning and learning-enabled components for decision making and perception of the environment, agents, and dynamics.

We propose to address this problem by designing a novel cognitive architecture for SA in multi-agent systems, enabling safe collaboration of autonomous vehicles (AVs) and drones. However, as these two types of agents are envisioned to function in practical real-life applications, in addition to communicating between each other, they will also need to interact with human users - drivers, pedestrians, drone operators, etc. Thus, modeling and implementing a SA architecture also requires an understanding of the requirements for building a trustworthy human-agent interaction.

In this paper, we present our ongoing work on modeling a communication module for our situational awareness architecture. We present a draft of our architecture, we ground the research in the scenario of driver-AV interaction, and we attempt to investigate the effect of the AV's autonomy on the human driver, as well as explore which parameters of the interaction have the highest impact on the user's sense of trust in the AV. Finally, we discuss our preliminary findings from the user study on their communication requirements, and propose a module for communication to be integrated in our awareness architecture.

1 INTRODUCTION

“Awareness” refers to the state of being conscious or mindful of the surroundings. In a broader sense, an agent with awareness possesses the ability to know and perceive the presence of things happening externally or internally. Given the rapid advancement of technology and the increasing presence of autonomous robotic devices in our daily life, introducing awareness in these artificial agents is an inevitable task [3].

Applications like intelligent transportation rely on multiple agents collaborating to accomplish shared objectives. This collaborative framework is referred to as multi-agent systems (MASs), which can consist of physical robots or virtual agents [6]. Introducing awareness to artificial agents within a MAS scenario serves multiple objectives: awareness drives the agents to perceive and understand the intentions, actions, and states of other agents in the system; and enables them to exhibit *cooperative* behavior, *coordinating* their actions and collaborating towards common goals efficiently and effectively [1, 28]. Awareness in MASs helps to develop *adaptive decision-making* [5] and facilitate *task allocation* and *resource management* among the agents by efficiently *planning* and *executing* the tasks while *avoiding conflicts* [15].

Moreover, having the ability to *communicate* and exchange information effectively also assists the agents in achieving their objectives. Communication within a MAS can take various forms, such as message passing, shared memory, negotiation and agreement protocols, ontologies and semantic communication, and perception-based exchanges [20]. However, while incorporating a communication architecture with computational reasoning and learning-enabled components can foster a sense of autonomy among MASs (and among the different agents in the same MAS), we also envision these agents implemented in practical real-life applications where they will interact with human users.

This poses an important research question: *how can these agents establish communication with human agents and achieve a personalized and socially appropriate interaction?* Modeling a representation of the human agents requires developing an understanding of their intentions and preferences [12, 21]. However, when developing technologies that will be used by people, we also need to investigate all of the implications for building a trustworthy and ethical human-agent interaction (HAI) [7, 9]. As the artificial agent will not have the same type of awareness as the human, we need to investigate how the agent's autonomy impacts the human, as well as which HAI parameters have the highest impact on the user's sense of trust in the agent.

We approach this by conducting user-centered studies [27] with potential end users, in which we discuss interaction scenarios, analyze the information the agent with awareness is processing and

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using in its decision-making, and develop the users' requirements for a trustworthy interaction.

The first interaction scenario we tackle in our research is the one between an autonomous vehicle (AV) and a human in the role of its driver. We conducted a small participatory design study consisting of two different interaction scenarios, where we presented to the participants the situational awareness information that the AV would be processing at any moment, and then worked together to discuss how this information should be shared with the users, as well as how the AV can take note of any potential user preferences.

In this paper, we present a draft of our situational awareness (SA) architecture, the preliminary findings from our first study with end users, and our ongoing work on integrating the user requirements and preferences in a communication module for our multi-agent architecture. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Sect. 2 presents our architecture for situational awareness; Sect. 3 presents our first participatory design study; Sect. 4 proposes a draft of the communication module, and Sect. 5 summarizes our findings and outlines our next steps.

2 PROPOSED MAS ARCHITECTURE FOR SITUATIONAL AWARENESS

An agent-oriented perspective is valuable in conceptualizing processes within a socio-technical system, as it views the system as comprising multiple agents, with the overall system behavior emerging from the individual processes of these agents and their interactions. A detailed survey of MAS covering a formal definition, features, applications, and challenges is available in [4].

In our work we propose a novel architecture for MASs, providing a comprehensive framework that incorporates knowledge, perception, communication, situational awareness, planning, and control to enable effective coordination and functioning of the MAS. The first draft of our architecture is shown in Fig. 1. A concise overview of each component follows below.

- **Knowledge.** In a MAS, the knowledge base is a component that stores and manages relevant information that can be useful to the coordination, collaboration, learning, adaptation, and decision-making processes of the agent [22]. In our architecture the knowledge base is a repository of information (about the environment, itself, other agents etc.) that the agent can access and utilize to perform its tasks effectively.

- **Estimation and Perception.** The estimation and perception block provides insight of the world around the agent and enables it to make informed decisions [25]. The agent uses various sensing mechanisms to gather data from the environment, which is then interpreted and processed by using intelligent algorithms (signal processing techniques, object recognition, etc) to transform the raw sensory data into a representation to be used for decision-making.

- **Communication.** Communication refers to the exchange of information, messages, and signals between the agents. In a MAS, this facilitates the coordination, collaboration, task allocation, and adaptation [20]. It enhances the effectiveness and intelligence of the system, enabling agents to work together towards common goals and achieve the desired outcomes.

- **Situational Awareness.** Situational awareness provides agents with a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics of the system

and facilitates effective decision-making [2]. In Fig. 1, the SA has four components: (i) *state*, which represents the current state of the system integrated with information about the environment, such as the presence of objects, obstacles, or changes in the surroundings; (ii) *intent*, which infers the intentions of other agents in the system by observing and interpreting their actions, and behaviors to understand their goals and motives; (iii) *uncertainty*, which represents the handling of the inherent uncertainty and incomplete information present in the environment and the perception module; and (iv) *risk*, which helps to assess the potential risks and hazards in the system by detecting any obstacles, anomalies, or changes in the environment, so as to identify potential threats or dangers.

- **Planning and Control.** The planning and control module utilizes the information provided by the SA module and generates actions that guide the behavior of the entire system towards the desired goal. The *planning* component devises a strategy that aligns with the intended objectives, while the *control* implements the devised strategy on the actual system.

- **Physical State of the System.** The physical state of the system encompasses the dynamic behavior of the system under consideration. The control actions implemented by the system directly influence and modify the physical state. The modulations in the physical state and the changes in the environment are subsequently fed back to the estimation and perception module. Thus, the proposed architecture establishes a feedback loop, where the components continuously update as the system advances toward its goal.

3 HUMAN UNDERSTANDING THROUGH USER-CENTERED DESIGN

Since implementing a SA architecture for agents that will interact with humans requires also an understanding of what is a trustworthy HAI [16, 24], we decided to conduct a series of participatory design studies with the end users. With this, we wished to uncover any potential *ethical issues* with the interaction scenarios, as well as explore the concept of *human oversight*. Specifically, we wished to investigate how the artificial agent's autonomy may impact the human users, and which facets of the interaction have the highest impact on the user's sense of trust in it. To explore this, we formulated the following research questions for our first study:

- *To what extent should the artificial agent act autonomously?*
- *How can human users be in the loop and monitor the interaction?*

As our MAS architecture is envisioned to be implemented in use cases with autonomous vehicles (AVs) and multi-drone systems, we opted to ground our first study in the scenario of human-AV interaction, with the human user being placed specifically in the role of the driver of the AV. We designed a workshop study to answer our research questions by exploring the relation between the level of trust a person would put in an AV, their driver behavior and experience, and any negative attitudes they may have towards AVs.

3.1 Participants

Fifteen participants took part in the study, four forming a pilot group, and the other eleven the four workshop groups. The age range was 18-39 yrs, and the gender ratio was 5:6:4 (F:M:X).

Figure 1: The proposed architecture of an awareness enabled MAS. The architecture provides insights into the internal structure of an agent i , which interacts with another agent j through the communication module.

3.2 Experimental Design and Protocol

The workshop group size varied between two and four members, and an experiment session lasted between 75-90 mins, with the workshop part being the most varied in length depending on the group dynamics.

At the start, participants filled one questionnaire on demographics (including information regarding their driver experience), and one on their driver behavior (an adapted and abridged version of the DBQ [17]). This was followed by a presentation on AVs¹ which introduced participants to the term, outlined the types of information the AV processes when making its decisions, and presented participants with the concepts on autonomy in AVs and how it's quantified (we used the SAE's Levels of Autonomy [8]). It also broached the concept of social interaction with AVs, and what it entails. After the presentation, participants filled the last questionnaire, which was an adaptation of the NARS [14], aimed at identifying and quantifying any negative attitudes or preconceptions participants may have towards AVs. The adapted version (referred to as AV-NARS) had less items than the original NARS (10 instead of 14), and they were adapted to fit the context of interaction with AVs, e.g. - "I would feel nervous operating a robot in front of other people." became "I would feel nervous driving an autonomous car while other people could observe me.". This concluded the first part of the experiment, which lasted about 30 minutes for each group.

The second part was the interactive workshop, comprising two use case scenarios (presented to users as series of computer-generated images²). In both of them, the participants had to imagine

themselves in the role of the driver of the AV (i.e. as sitting in the driver seat in the AV).

In the first scenario (Fig. 2), the AV was driving at 100 km/h on a busy highway in the middle lane. The next scene showed a second car merging onto the highway from the right side at an unsafe distance and speed, risking impending collision.

Figure 2: Highway driver-AV scenario. AI-generated images of a car's dashboard with the driver's POV, car driving on a busy highway and another car cutting in from the right.

In the second scenario (Fig. 3), the AV was driving at 40 km/h on an unfamiliar suburban street, with no other cars, humans, or animals around. The scenario continued with the AV suddenly slowing down to 20 km/h without any visible obstacle in view. The final scene showed a school that was previously obscured behind trees and thus not visible to the human driver until then.

The workshop was focused on two activities - modulating the **Level of Autonomy (LoA)**, and designing a **user interface** for interaction between the car and the driver. The levels of autonomy we worked with in this study were the SAE-defined Levels 0 through 3 (see Fig.4), and the process of modulating them was visually represented by a dial which participants could adjust in each scene.

¹In the study, participants were familiarized with the phrase "autonomous vehicles" but they also referred to the embodied agent in question as a "self-driving car". This paper likewise uses the two terms interchangeably, although the authors acknowledge that AVs include not only self-driving cars but also other ground or air vehicles.

²Images generated with <https://openai.com/dall-e-2>

Figure 3: Suburbs driver-AV scenario. AI-generated images of a car's dashboard with the driver's POV, car driving on an empty neighborhood street, with a school building coming up on the left.

For each scene in both scenarios, participants were asked to select the highest level of autonomy they were comfortable with, both on an individual level, and as a group.

Level - 0	Level - 1	Level - 2	Level - 3	Level - 4	Level - 5
DRIVER	FEET OFF	HANDS OFF	EYES OFF	MIND OFF	PASSENGER
No Assistance	Assisted	Partially Automated	Highly Automated	Fully Automated	Autonomous
Human	Transfer of responsibility				Machine

Figure 4: The six SAE Levels of Autonomy. In our study we worked with Levels 0 to 3, i.e. "Driver", "Feet off", "Hands off", and "Eyes off".

The second workshop activity utilized the information that the AV uses to calculate its SA and select its next action. We defined three categories of information:

- *State of the AV*: a combination of its position, speed, and eventual acceleration.
- *State of the environment*:
 - distance between AV and objects (pedestrians, other cars, buildings, cattle, ...)
 - type of objects: *dynamic* (pedestrians, cars, ...) or *static* (signs, buildings, ...)
 - traffic rules that need to be followed in the current AV state
- *Actions of the AV*: startup, drive at normal speed, speed up, slow down, stop.

For each scenario participants were asked to work together as a group to design the interface for the AV, deciding on the amount and type of information they wanted shown. The designed interface was then considered through all scenes of each scenario, and any eventual modifications were made during the scene changes.

3.3 Data collection

We collected data from three main sources during our study:

- *Questionnaires*. Participants answered questionnaires on demographics, adapted DBQ (driver behavior questionnaire) and adapted AV-NARS (negative attitudes towards AVs).

- *Creative/visual workshop*. For each group there were two flipchart sheets (one per scenario) that contained the image representations of the scenes of the scenario, the collage of the post-its depicting the user interface the group designed, and the dial for the LoA.

- *Audio recordings*. In addition to the visual data from the workshop, we also conducted audio recordings of each group during that part. While the audio recordings were not used for the scope of this work, we plan to rely on them heavily to inform the design of our following study.

3.4 Data analysis

Although we have yet to conduct a full statistical analysis on the questionnaire and workshop data, we performed a preliminary Pearson Correlation Coefficient calculation for the results of the DBQ, AV-NARS and the average of the participants' individual levels of autonomy (LoA).

The analysis showed a very low correlation for DBQ / AV-NARS ($r(9)=0.0117$, $p=0.9728$), and for DBQ / LoA ($r(9)=0.1393$, $p=0.6829$), but a moderate negative correlation for AV-NARS / LoA ($r(9)=-0.449$, $p=0.1659$). This last finding suggests that the less negative attitudes towards AVs users may have, the higher the level of autonomy they'd be comfortable with the AV possessing, which is a valuable information for the design of AV systems.

Moreover, from the preliminary qualitative analysis of the workshop, we individuated two main designs for the interface: a minimal, unobtrusive interface similar to modern car GPS navigators; and a much more complex design containing visual depiction of all of the information the AV is processing and its upcoming actions.

Participants who opted for the first design tended to want explicit communication from the AV only in moments of emergencies (e.g. "another car is about to collide with me"), whereas the proponents of the second design wished to be able at any moment to see how the AV is processing and understanding the scene, and how it selects its actions. Among our next analyses, we will explore the correlation between the participants' preference on one design over the other and their AV-NARS and LoA scores.

4 DESIGNING A COMMUNICATION MODULE

In our SA framework, the AV agents can communicate explicitly between each other by way of transmitting their SA and perceptual information. However, our participatory study showed that we also need to design an interface for the human users to communicate with the AVs. For this issue, we decided to look to the field of social cognition and interaction, as well as existing cognitive frameworks and architectures [10].

Social cognition defines two forms of interaction between two cognitive agents (artificial or natural): *instrumental helping* and *collaboration* [23]. Helping is an interaction where the active, helping agent wishes to assist the passive agent by identifying their goal, inferring their intent, recognizing that they require help, and acting to provide help to them [26]. Collaboration instead is a more reciprocal interaction, as both agents contribute equally and work

Figure 5: The revised version of the architecture, the human communication interface and corresponding module connections highlighted in green.

together to achieve a common goal, through sharing their intent and attention, and engaging in joint action.

As the human-agent interaction in our MAS (grounded in our use cases for AVs and multi-drone systems) has more of an assistive nature, we view instrumental helping as closer to the intent of our agents. Instrumental helping has two components, a cognitive one and an emotional (or motivational) one. The cognitive component seeks to understand the goal of the passive agent, and why they require help; whereas the motivational component drives the helping agent to act, wishing to see the passive agent achieve its goal.

However, while in artificial cognitive agents these components are usually implicit and internal - with the agent having Theory of Mind and advanced perceptual abilities to understand the human's intent and goal [12], as well as internal motivational system to drive the agent to help [13] - the preliminary findings from our study showed that users preferred a very explicit communication instead.

A majority of participants responded that “they would feel uneasy if the AV could recognize their emotions”, and expressed their preference of a simpler explicit interface where the artificial agent wouldn't do any implicit detection of their intent. Taking in considerations these requirements, we propose in Fig. 5 an expansion of our architecture, where the human agent can explicitly set the goal for the interaction, and express their preferences for how much information they want communicated, which the agent can then provide via the communication interface.

5 DISCUSSION

In this paper, we presented a novel MAS architecture, integrating multiple cognitive components such as knowledge, perception, communication, situational awareness, planning, and control, with the aim to facilitate efficient coordination and decision-making. Given the practical nature of the artificial agents in the MAS and

their operation in environments influenced by humans, their communication needed to extend beyond interaction with other agents and to include active engagement with the human operators and users. For this we relied on user-centered design methods in our work, so as to include the end users from the start in the design and implementation process and enable a reliable and trustworthy human-agent interaction.

Our preliminary findings informed the design of a communication interface that presents the awareness information and intended actions of the artificial agent to the human user. However, we also became aware of a gap that has still not been bridged in cognitive HAI, namely - *how can we reconcile existing models of social cognition for HAI with the preferences of human users?*

Additionally, we are also aware that there has been recent research in the field of human-AV interaction showing that road users tend to favor implicit communication when in traffic [11], and that some studies are starting to look at the implications of this in AV design [18, 19]. While in our framework we currently rely on explicit communication only, we will also consider how to potentially expand this to include implicit HMI features as well.

In our next steps, we will conduct detailed qualitative and statistical analysis of the workshop data to further explore the correlations between people's trust in the agents and their preferences for the communication. We will rely on these findings for the design of our follow-up study, where we will aim to present modeling techniques from social cognition to the participants, work together with them to uncover any ethical or trustworthiness issues they may have with the design, and understand how we can reconcile the existing models of cognitive interaction with the user requirements.

By integrating these findings, we aim to create a more interactive, adaptive, and trustworthy framework where the artificial agents will be able to actively consider and incorporate the human inputs into their decision-making processes. We view this integration

as having the potential to improve the overall performance and effectiveness of the multi-agent system by leveraging the cognitive capabilities of both humans and machines, as well as contribute to more natural, trustworthy, and long-term interaction between humans and artificial agents.

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